

SIMULATION AND VERIFICATION OF CURE-INDUCED DEFORMATION FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Cure induced deformation of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites brings many problems to parts assembly. A multi-level simulation method for cure process of composite integrated structure was developed to simplify calculation and improve accuracy of prediction. Several simplified models were involved in multi-level simulation method. Thermal shrinkage, cure shrinkage and mold effect were considered in analysis models. Panels, L-shape beams, stiffened panels and sandwich structures were manufactured to verify the simulation method. It is found that numerical predictions compared quite well with experimental measurements. The results show that the adopted simulation method can be used to predict the cure-induced deformation for different kinds of structures, with accuracy of 85% more or less.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials have been widely used in aircraft, automobile and sporting goods.^[1] Integrated process is an important technique for composites to reduce parts and fasteners and meet the needs of structure performance. Cure-induced deformation is a key problem to improve process quality of large-scale and complex integrated structure made of composite materials. For reducing cure-induced deformation, conventional method is to adjust and correct the skin of mold and cure system again and again according as experiences and process tests. But this kind of trial and error method increases fabrication cost. So it is important to develop a simulation method of predicting cure-induced deformation for composite structures, to guarantee product quality and reduce fabrication cost.^[2]

Investigations have been developed into cure-induced deformation and residual stress distribution for composites. Yi^[3] et al. developed a nonlinear finite element model to analyze the residual stresses in thermoset composites during cool-down after curing. Lee and Sohn^[4] added the residual stresses in the curing period to the thermal stresses in the cool-down period to make up the total residual stress. Yoon and Kim^[5] researched the effect of thermal deformation and chemical shrinkage on the process-induced distortion of carbon/epoxy curved laminates. Nuri Ersoy and Kevin Potter^[6] considered that composite parts manufactured by autoclave processes had manufacturing distortions due to unavoidable physical mechanisms that took place during the process. Kim and Daniel^[7] applied a more direct method to measure the strain in the cure process. They used fiber Bragg grating and resistance strain chip buried inside the composite materials to measure the changing of the strain. It was found that the reciprocity between mold and part leads to evident strain in the cure process. Satish^[8] applied

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shear layer to replace the influence of mold on the composite material by simulation. The method can accurately predict the curing deformation generated by the reciprocity between mold and part.

In this study, a multi-level simulation method for cure process of composite structures was developed. Several simplified models were involved in multi-level simulation method, including equivalent temperature load model and shear layer model. Thermal deformation, cure shrinkage and mold effect were considered in analysis. Panels, L-shape beams, stiffened panels and sandwich structures were made to verify the simulation method.

2 MULTI-LEVEL SIMULATION METHOD

Figure 1: Multi-level simulation method to predict cure-induced deformation

In multi-level simulation method, cure-induced deformation of different kinds of composite structures was investigated in order of structure complexity. Cure-induced deformation of complex structures was predicted based on solutions obtained from studies of simple composite structures. Additional factors were taken into model to adapt to structural characteristic when the studied composite structure became more complex. Totally, three factors were taken into consideration, including thermal shrinkage, cure shrinkage and mold effect. But the deformation induced by these three factors had different ratio with respect to different kinds of structures. The objective of multi-level simulation method is to predict cure-induced deformation of real complex composite structures, so the model used must be as simplified as possible. Therefore, subordinate effect factors could be neglected to reach a balance between predicting accuracy and time cost. And some semi-empirical models are suitable to be selected.

a) Equivalent temperature load model

In autoclave processing, the shrinkage of composite material (ε^{total}) consists of two parts: cure shrinkage (denoted as ε^h) aroused by cure reaction of resin and thermal shrinkage (denoted as ε^r) taking place in cooling stage after resin was cured completely, as described in equation (1).^[9]

$$\varepsilon^{total} = \varepsilon^h + \varepsilon^r \quad (1)$$

ε^r depends on the thermal expansion coefficient of composites. ε^h is related to the complex cure reaction of resin and is difficult to simulate. A semi-empirical model was proposed to regard ε^h as an equivalent temperature load. In equivalent temperature load model, complex cure reaction is not taken into consideration and a lot of iterative computations were avoided.

$$\varepsilon^r = \alpha \Delta T^r \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon^h = \alpha \Delta T^h \quad (3)$$

then

$$\varepsilon^{total} = \alpha(\Delta T^r + \Delta T^h) \quad (4)$$

where α represents the thermal expansion coefficient of composites that have cured completely. ΔT^r represents the difference between cure temperature and room temperature. ΔT^h represented the equivalent temperature difference.

As

$$\varepsilon^h / \varepsilon^r = \Delta T^h / \Delta T^r \quad (5)$$

then

$$\Delta T^h = \Delta T^r \cdot \varepsilon^h / \varepsilon^r \quad (6)$$

$\varepsilon^h / \varepsilon^r$ could be obtained from fiber Bragg grating experiments. Finally, the equivalent temperature difference was determined according to equation (6).

Figure 2: Bragg grating experiment results

b) Shear layer model

There is a large body of evidence confirming the occurrence of tool-part interaction. The thermal expansion coefficient difference between composites and mold will contribute to cure-induced deformation. A shear layer was added to the surface of composites in touch with mould. The shear layer is part of the composites and acts in the temperature rising period after the gelling point of composites. Because of the shear layer, there was a stress gradient in the thickness direction of composites. Shear layer has two parameters: thickness (t_s) and thermal expansion coefficient (α_s). Shear layer parameters (t_s and α_s) were determined from unidirectional laminate experiments ($[0]_3$, $[0]_4$, $[0]_5$, $[0]_6$).

Figure 3: unidirectional laminate experiments

Figure 4: t_s and α_s determination

3.2 laminates

Figure 5: Asymmetric panels

Label	Stack sequence	Experimental maximum warpage /mm	Simulation /mm	Error /%
1	[45/90 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0 ₂ /45]	3	2.8	6.67
2	[0 ₃ /45 ₄]	12.5	11.6	7.20
3	[0/0/45/45]	13.5	16.4	21.48
4	[0/0/45/0]	13.5	10.7	20.74
5	[0/90/-45 ₂ /90/0/45 ₂]	14	12.3	12.14
6	[0/0/45/-45]	15.5	15.5	0.00
7	[90/90/45/45]	17.5	13.8	21.14
8	[90/45/45/0]	18.5	16.5	10.81
9	[90/90/90/45]	27.5	23.3	15.27
10	[90/90/45/-45]	30.5	28.0	8.20

Table 1: Simulation and experimental results of asymmetric panels

Ten laminates with asymmetric stack sequence were manufactured to verify the multi-level simulation method. Laminate geometry was 150*75 mm. Simulation and experimental results are shown in Table 1. Value of cure induced deformation lied between 2 to 30 mm. Predicting accuracy of multi-level simulation method was 85% more or less.

3.3 L-shaped beams

Figure 6: laminates made of woven fabric reinforced composite: (a) experimental results, (b) simulation results.

With regard to woven fabric reinforced composite that fiber volume percentage was equal in warp and weft direction, there was no cure-induced deformation for laminates, even if the panel had an asymmetric stack sequence.

But as for structures that were more complex than panels, cure-induced deformation occurred. It was observed that during the manufacture of L-shaped beams, a reduction in the enclosed angle build up. This is because in the cylindrical segment of L-shape beam, the out-of-plane thermal contraction is higher than the in-plane contraction. Deformation is characterized by $\Delta\theta$,

$$\Delta\theta = \theta_1 - \theta_2 \quad (7)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 represent the enclosed angle of L-shape beams before and after curing processing.

Figure 7: L-shape beams made of woven fabric reinforced composite: (a) geometry, (b) experimental results, (c) simulation results.

Stack sequence	$\Delta\theta$ (Simulation)	$\Delta\theta$ (experimental)	error
[0/0/45/45/45/45/45/45]	1.25	1.37	9.6%
[45]8	1.25	1.37	9.6%
[45/45/0/45/45/45/45]s	1.25	1.37	9.6%

Table 2: Simulation and experimental results of L-shaped beams

Simulation and experimental results are listed in Table. 2. For L-shaped beams, predicting accuracy of multi-level simulation method is 90% more or less. It is found that cure-induced deformation of L-shaped beams has no relations to stack sequence or ply thickness.

Considering the deformation feature of panels and L-shaped beams, using woven fabric reinforced composites is conducive to deformation controlling.

3.3 Stiffened panels

Figure 8: geometry of stiffened panels.

Figure 9: Simulation and actual deformation of stiffened panels under co-cure

Figure 10: Simulation and actual deformation of stiffened panels under co-bonding with cured stringer and uncured skin

Figure 11: Simulation and actual deformation of stiffened panels under co-bonding with cured skin and uncured stringer

Process	The maximal displacement of skin		Error%
	Experimental	Simulation	
Co-cure	39.2	36.1	8.01
Co-bonding(cured stringer)	34.4	31.4	8.72
Co-bonding(cured skin)	35.9	32.3	10.0

Table 3: The maximal displacement of skin at different curing scheme

Simulation and experimental results of stiffened panels are displayed in Figure. 9-11 and Table. 3. Deformation trend predicted by multi-level model is consistent with experimental results. Prediction accuracy is more than 80%. With regard to stiffened panels, a special problem is curing scheme. Different curing schemes lead to deformation variation, but this kind of difference is limited. A stress transfer model was utilized to describe the effect of curing scheme on deformation.^[10] Due to limited space, the stress transfer model is not introduced here.

3.4 Sandwich structures

Figure 12: Simulation and experimental results of sandwich structures

Because of the sandwich design, cure-induced deformation of semi-cylinder is relatively small. Prediction accuracy remains more than 80%.

4 CONCLUSION

A multi-level simulation method for cure process of composite integrated structure was developed to simplify calculation and improve accuracy of prediction. Equivalent temperature load model and shear layer model were introduced. A mass of experiments were carried out to verify the multi-level simulation method, including panels, L-shape beams, stiffened panels and sandwich structures. Results show that the adopted simulation method can be used to predict the cure-induced deformation for different kinds of structures, with accuracy of 80%.

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